

Bird perception survey

The following questionnaire will consist in four sections:

1. Respondent personal information
2. Perceptions about six bird species in specific environments of a coastal city
3. The origin of those species
4. Questions about the coastal urban environments

Section 1.

You will be asked for some personal information, which will be kept confidential.

<p>Name of interviewer</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>Age of respondent</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>¿What is your main activity when visiting the coastline?</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>Date</p> <input type="text" value="2019-06-01"/>	<p>Género</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Female</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Male</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Other</p>	<p>Which is your favorite bird from the coast?</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>Site</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>How many people are there in your household?</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>What grade would you give to your knowledge of birds?</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>Survey ID</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>Occupation of respondent</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>Have you participated in any bird watching activity or workshop about birds?</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> No, never</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes, sometimes</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes, many times</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes, always</p>
<p>Resident or visitant of the coast</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Resident</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Resident</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Both</p>	<p>Income (Chilean pesos/CLP)</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Less than \$300.000</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Between \$300.000 and \$550.000</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Between \$550.000 and \$1.450.000</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Between \$1.450.000 and \$2.400.000</p> <p><input type="radio"/> More than \$2.400.000</p>	<p>Where or part of what?</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>How long do you live from the coast (m)?</p> <input type="text"/>		

Section 2.

You will be presented with six birds, and some questions will be asked about your familiarity to them

SPECIES 1

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

SPECIES 2

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

SPECIES 3

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

SPECIES 4

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

SPECIES 5

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

SPECIES 6

Do you recognize this bird?

- Yes
 No

Can you tell me the common name of this species?

For each one of this six environments, please respond according to how you fell about this species

Green Area

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urban core

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Urbanized beach

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Natural rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Modified rocky shore

If you were to come to this place 7 days a week, how many days would you expect to see this bird?

Please rate your level of satisfaction, on a scale of 1 to 7, with being close to this bird in this location, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

Section 3.

You will be asked about the same six bird species, but this time regarding their origin. Can you indicate for each one of them whether they are marine or terrestrial species?

- Terrestrial
- Marine
- Do not know

- Terrestrial
- Marine
- Do not know

Section 4 4.

You will be presented with the same six environments as seen before.
Please respond based on what you think about each of them.

Visits to Green Areas

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied'.

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same

Visits to Urban Core

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied'.

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same

Visits to Natural Beach

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same

Visits to Urbanized Beach

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same

Visits to Natural Rocky Shore

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same

Visits to Modified Rocky Shore

Please rate your level of satisfaction when seeing birds in this environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 represents 'not at all satisfied' and 7 represents 'very satisfied.'

What do you like the most of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I like birds here because they are pleasing to the eye or have pleasant songs.)
- Behavior (I like to see birds here when they are feeding, flying, walking, or perching)
- Place (I like birds here because they are common to see and make me feel at home.)
- Spiritual (I like birds here because they provide or transmit spiritual values to me, or I like birds here because they connect me with nature)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

What do you like the least of seeing birds in this environment?

- Aesthetic (I do not like birds here because they are unpleasant or noisy to look at.)
- Behavior (I do not like birds here because their droppings make a mess on people's properties or concern me about health or safety.)
- Place (I do not like birds here because they are too common to see or/and can be aggressive or intimidating.)
- Spiritual (I do not like birds because they provide negative feelings or sensations.)
- There is nothing that I like here
- Other

Frequency of visits

- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year

In relation to your childhood, how would you describe the change in your visits to this environment over time?

- Have increased over time
- Have decreased over time
- Have remain the same